

Brain Drain: A Serious Threat for Indian Intellectual Youth, Economy and Nationalism

**Ms. POONAM PANDITA¹ Mr. SACHIN KUMAR² Ms. PARUL ANTHAL³ Ms. CHETNA SURI⁴
Ms. SHIVALI VERMA⁵**

Research Scholar, Dept. of Educational Studies Central University of Jammu

Research Scholar, Dept. of Educational Studies Central University of Jammu

Teacher Educator, Dept. of Educational Studies Central University of Jammu

Teacher Educator, Dept. of Educational Studies Central University of Jammu

Research Scholar, Dept. of Educational Studies Central University of Jammu

Email- shivaliverma898@gmail.com

Email- poonampandita001@gmail.com

Email- sachinchoudhary8282@gmail.com

Email- sachinchoudhary8282@gmail.com

Email- parulanthal468@gmail.com

Email- chetnasuriguptagmail.com

Abstract

After 75 Years of Independence of India is mere in the list of developing countries. The main reason beyond this is the Brain Drain which is a serious threat for Indian Education System, Economy and Nationalism. Developed Countries offered Sponsorship schemes, Scholarship schemes, higher salary packages and hire the most intellectual Youth of India which affects Our Country in all perspectives and also become a great barrier for the development of our Nation. Many legends of India like Ramanujan, Vivekananda, ShriAurobindo, M.K Gandhi, Dr.A.P.J Abdul Kalam inspired by their dedication towards Nationalism time to time by serving their own Nation though Indian can regain their ancient position back in World. Reverse Brain Drain also plays a vital role to migrate it's skilled persons back to their motherland and serve here with full devotion. The main findings of this paper is Developed Countries manipulated the Indian Intellectual, Capable, Skilled Students by Brain Drain due to which Indian Economy suffered a lot. Our strong ancient Indian Education System and the continue efforts of Indian Government succeeded not completely but in rare points which results Reverse Brain Drain.

Keywords: Brain Drain, Economy, Education System, Nationalism

Introduction

India will celebrate 76th years of Independence on 15th August 2022. In last year India celebrated its National festival with an idea to 'Create a Vision' and highlighted the scientific and technological achievements and advancements. No doubt, India has now step towards Smart cities first time in the world history and this scheme was launched by the current Prime Minister Sh. Narendra Modi on 25th June 2015 with the agenda 100 Smart cities in five zones of India i.e. North, East, West, South and Central India. Govt. of India now moderate India with all aspects. It taken its first step from the roots of Indian Society which is Education. For this MHRD set several new universities in every state of India whether these are Central or State universities, they focused on quality Education with well equipped Infrastructure. According to the list Central Universities published on 31st March 2021 there are 54 Central universities existed in India with the current date. According to the Survey on Higher Education in year 2020 there are 1043 universities across India with highly qualified Professors, Infrastructure and Scholarship schemes. Many new IIT's, Medical Institutions, Agricultural Institutions, Art and Craft etc. came under these fully developed Educational Institutions. These all Universities not only provided quality Education and a better placement in eminent

Companies and Industries of India as well as abroad also.

As, Indian Government put every possible effort for the Quality Education, Employment, Societies of Indian Citizens but it is still came under developing Countries list in World. So, the question raised here that Is the only Indian Government is responsible for this position of India in World after many years of Independence of India Or something else? Then the answer is No according the literature review. As, there are many reasons for this but the main reason beyond this that the lack of Nationalism in the Indian Citizens due to which they face the corruption problem in every sector of India. Lack of Nationalism creates a brain drain problem in students due to which India suffered a lot not only but many other under developing countries face this issue also. The UN world Migration Report 2022 said that India has 3.2 Million well educated migrant working in developed countries like U.S.A, U.N, Canada, Russia, Australia etc. These countries attract the under developing countries students by their sponsored schemes, Scholarships, part time as well as full time jobs with higher Salary packages. These developed countries indirectly fulfill the demand of their Industries workers with the already well skilled and intellectual minds as their economy is stronger than Indian rupees so, they hire easily the young minds of our Country. But the Nationalism of India is suffered with this serious

threat from the colonial Era to the present date. Only the awareness of Nationalism in Indian youth Intellectual minds can attain reverse brain drain and make their nation strong not only from their inner core but economically also.

Objectives

1. Awaken Feeling of Nationalism in Indian University Students towards Nationalism by National Education.
2. Inspire Students about Nationalism by discussing Great Indian Reformers.
3. To disuse Abolish Brain drain which is serious threat for Nationalism
4. Aware students the main target of developed countries beyond Brain Drain.
5. To discuss Reverse Brain drain for Development of Nationalism in Students.

Discussion

From Ancient India to the till date only Education has that power to deal with the every problem of human life whether it's about strong , peaceful, Intellectual, Unity or a great Nation. Education has the power to eradicate castism, racism, and cultural, linguistic distances of a country's citizen and build a strong Nation. And in the world India set a. Perfect example for all this. India is a land of ancient scriptures, well versed literature, well Intellectual minds and many more. One great example of this that Indian has a strong identity in world from the ancient period though it has the most eminent universities like Taxila, Nalanda, Ujjain in it's womb. These universities had a strong education system which attracted every corner of the world. Chinese scholars like Fahien, XunXang etc. Came there for higher education and resided here for many years and kept with them many written manuscripts based on Indian Education System, Value System, Enrich Culture, Administration System etc. But the many foreign invaders not only destroyed these Educational universities but also plundered the enrich source of Indian cultural sources i.e. Temples. Somnath Temple is one of them which was plundered and destroyed by invaders about Seventeen times. The main reason beyond to the destruction of this the stronger countries frightened from the enrich Education System of India So that they tried to vanish their literature and burnt the Nalanda University. After the destruction of these Ancient Indian Universities our country's Nationalism faced a dark Era because every ruling country Introduce their culture and Education System in India. Even they propagated their Religion by missionaries. When India was the colony of Britain they set up limitations on Indian's Education System and only provided them the Education According to their East India companies demand. But Education awakens the Nationalism in Indians and they fight for their

rights, For the Independence of their Country, for the development of their country etc. Nowadays where every Student is busy with their professional life and forgets feeling of Nationalism inside them. This technological Era need to back the roots of Indian Education System. No doubt it's technological Era where every developed country have strong atomic powers, Technological Systems, Moderate cities with well planned system etc. But the only country which leads them as a peace Guru that is Our Nation India. It's possible because India is the land of the legendaries who create their own formulas in mathematics i.e. Ramanujan, Arybhata who gave zero to World, Patanjali who was the founder of Yoga systems, Vivekananda who influenced western countries by their Nationalism etc. Indian Education System must balance the Nationalism and progress of the Students together. Nationalism helps a nation to strengthen it's roots in all aspects whether it's economy, integration, leading Country etc. This land is the mother of many legendaries as we all knows and these legendaries set up an example as served themselves towards their nation time to time. ShriAurobindo, RabindranathTagore, M. k Gandhi awaken the Nationalism though which the Indians attain Independence. It was the only their literature which ignite the spark inside the millions of Indians and they fought with unity. They made education as a weapon against these strong nations darkness and attain the Sunshine of their Country. After Independence many Committees and Educational policies were implemented by Government of India for the betterment of Indians. Because the Indian Government well knows that only the Education can help its citizens to get back our Country's ancient position back. Not only Indian Government but today many businessman and Industrialists also taken initiative for this. Rattan Tata who is an eminent Industrialist and former Chairman of Tata Sons awarded more than 5400 Students till date with the JN Tata Endowment's loan Scholarship since 1892 to higher Studies. So, that the student's can service their own country. Another great personality is DhirubhaiAmbani who is the Number one business person of India provided scholarship to meritorious and especially able students of class 12th. But why the Independent India mere standing in the developing countries list till date. As, the many legendaries set up an example of Nationalism in Indian history. The reason beyond this the many rich citizens start this process in late 60's after the World war 2nd when India suffered with unemployment they migrated to the developed Countries and settled their and never return back to their motherland India.

Brain Drain: The concept is popularized in 1960's as per the sources and this term means

that the migration of a skilled, capable, educated, Intellectual person to a developed Country.

Developed countries like U.S.A, China, and Russia etc. Provided Scholarship, sponsored, high salary packages to the anxious youth Intellectual minds who desires a luxurious life. These Students attracted towards these countries packages as they have lack of Nationalism. Sometimes they have full feelings for their Nation but the unemployment and less packages effects also become the reason for their migration. So, these countries also give them work permits also give citizenship after their terms and conditions. Due to which the developing countries suffered a lot and it effects it's economy and also a threat for their Nationalism. These Developed Countries have a strong strategy of manipulation of the young minds as they are the old player's of this game from the ancient time, only they change the name of their strategy in ancient times they made colonies to the less developed Countries and force their citizens to serve them by forcefully. Now, they set up the schemes for the Young Students of under developing countries after they offered the big packages and instead of that they hired Intellectual precious minds of our country which serve them and represent their countries in World. When they assured with their dedication and hard work they give them citizenship and instead of that they permanently make colonies in their intellect. Many Nationalists believed that this happens because the lack of Nationalism. If a person balanced their Education System with the value and Nationalism Education System. He can develop a sense of Nationalism and stop their unwanted desires which force him to revolt against hsi nation. For example Dr. A.P.J Abdul kalam was a perfect example for this who invented the first Missile Of India and become Missile Man of India if he influenced with the Developed Countries Packages then Indian may not have their own missile and attained fame in the World. He not only invented missile but also motivate the Indian students time to time for their National development. He was very much interested to discuss the Country development goals with the young Intellectual minds of India and it's effect we seen today many Students inspired from him and have a strong National feeling with a great ambition in their life. Swami Vivekananda is also a role model of many Indian students who influenced whole European countries by their Nationalism and not left his Country behind the luxurious life Of European countries. He can choose that life but he choose his motherland and server for India only. He was well known for his pious, sacred, Spiritual and precious knowledge which he attain from the authentic literature of India and from his belief System. He knows European Countries may have the immense power in all sectors but that are weak in one section that is Peace. They may have

the advanced technologies but their technologies only can create blunders in world not satisfy their spirits with that. This is their strong belief system that's the result that India is leading whole world as Yogic and Peace Guru. Only Indian Education and belief system has the power that they regain their lost identity once again in the world by their Belief System. Government of India also take initiative to abolish brain drain by setting up new Educational Institutions and Universities and also provide Scholarships Schemes, placements and conducted many programmes for Specially professional Students though they can awaken Nationalism in them . As, India has facing Economical issues till date that Government of India aware the Students of India about their current position in Economic sector by setting conferences directly with the IITs, AIIMS, Agricultural and other Institutions Students that they can influence them to serve in their own country after their Education and develop their Country strong in all perspectives. Reverse Brain Drain is another term for the awaken Nationalism in the Students as well as the Abroad Settled Indian Skilled persons. Reverse Brain Drain is the effort of those countries towards their Nation which influenced their Migrated in their Countries back and provided them sufficient package and request them to serve in their own Countries for the development of their own Nation and represent trey own Country in World with their Spirit of Nationalism.

Suggestions

1. Conduct Debates, discussions, Conferences on Nationalism in Professional as well as academic Universities of India for creating a Feeling of Nationalism.
2. Indian Government set up a limit on abroad Work permit for highly skilled Intellectual Students of India.
3. Aware the students about the brain drain strategy of Developed Countries.
4. Indian Government includes only their own Companies and Industries for the placements of professional Institutions of India.
5. Indian Government takes initiative steps for the reverse brain drain.
6. Indian Private Sectors also take initiative to provide a job security assurance to the well educated and skilled student's of India.

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